

November 2021

Press Release

13 Innovative Data Solutions Join the 2nd Edition of the COVID-X Acceleration Programme

The COVID-X Open Call #2, running from early June until the 22nd of July 2021, attracted applications from a varied range of Start-Ups and SMEs around Europe, gathering 79 submitted applications from 24 countries.

By the 7th of August, the eligible applicants, meeting the key selection criteria, were selected for the 2nd application stage closing on the 15th of September. In the end, 37 applications were submitted. Now, the external evaluation process of the 2nd application phase is complete and the programme is happy to announce the selected candidates: **13 (RECAMOS3, AIDE-X, COVID-MRP, i-COVID, PREPARE, ART-COVID, Legit.Health COVID-1, suPARcharge, PAK Rehab, AIDA, OMMLOCO, TRAK COVID-19 and 2ti COVID-19)**. These teams come from 8 European countries: Switzerland, Portugal, Italy, The Netherlands, Spain, Greece, Denmark and United Kingdom.

COVID-X, supported by the European Commission under Horizon2020 Programme, runs a unique 10-month acceleration program for 30+ close-to-market data and AI-driven solutions boosting their market uptake to support healthcare systems and to save lives of coronavirus patients.

COVID-X will fund EU Companies and Healthcare Providers to boost data-driven solutions with the power to overcome challenges in Diagnosis, Prognosis, and Follow-up. The funding is invested in products with TRL 7+ and [or in the process of] CE marking, covering two profiles: single players (EU Tech SMEs / Start-Ups) validating their solutions at one of COVID-X clinical partners; or team (Tech Provider working with a Healthcare provider that will validate the solution).

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In addition to the direct funding, the COVID-X Programme provides the top-ranked solutions access in a tailored Acceleration Program organized in 3 sprints of 3 months, and that includes technical coaching business mentoring sessions as well as support in ethical issues and piloting with healthcare organizations. This 10-month program targets to boost the quick market uptake to defeat COVID-19 with data solutions.

COVID-X involves a consortium of 10 prominent partners from 7 different countries:

For more information

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